

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF FABRIC DEFORMATION MECHANISMS DURING PREFORM MANUFACTURE

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SUMMARY: In recent years, a number of fabric drape models have been developed, which are usually based on a kinematic algorithm in which deformation is restricted to inter-fibre shear. However relatively little experimental evidence has been reported to support this approach, and it is widely recognised that a number of other deformation mechanisms exist. The objective of this study was to investigate the formability of a range of non-crimp fabric reinforcements, both to validate the kinematic model and to quantify the effects of fabric construction on formability. The first stage involved analysing fabrics during pure shear, which showed that the fabric construction can greatly affect both the fabric shear stiffness and fibre locking angle. Fabric samples were then deformed using a hemispherical punch, with an automated strain analysis system used to measure the resulting fibre distribution. The predicted and measured fibre patterns agreed well up to the fibre locking angle, with fabric shear stiffness apparently having a negligible effect.

KEYWORDS: preforms, drape modelling, fabric shear, non-crimp fabrics, RTM, SRIM

INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite moulding processes, including resin transfer moulding (RTM) and structural reaction injection moulding (SRIM), are now finding widespread applications in the automotive and aerospace industries. These processes involve the impregnation of a fibre preform with a liquid thermosetting resin, which is then cured to produce a rigid component. Preforms are usually produced in a separate manufacturing process, with a wide range of techniques available for their manufacture. Whilst a number of textile based techniques can be used to produce preforms directly from yarns or rovings, these are usually limited to specific component geometries such as regular or prismatic sections and it is often necessary to produce preforms by forming or stamping of reinforcement mats or fabrics. However the formability of the reinforcements, which are often woven or stitch-bonded “non-crimp” fabrics, is limited by their construction. In particular fabric wrinkling can occur in areas with complex curvature, which would lead to rejection of the preform on grounds of quality. Another associated problem is that the resulting variations in fibre volume fractions and orientations can lead to a non-uniform distribution of both preform permeability and component mechanical properties, thus making preform design strategies based on flow simulation and structural analysis somewhat problematic.

To overcome some of the difficulties outlined above, in recent years a number of simulations have been developed for fabric deformation during preform manufacture. These are usually based on a kinematic mapping of an idealised fabric to an arbitrary surface, assuming the reinforcement to be analogous to a pin-jointed net. However it is widely recognised that a number of other deformation mechanisms exist, although relatively little experimental work has been reported to quantify these. The objective of this study was to establish the formability of a range of reinforcement fabrics and to investigate the validity of the kinematic model. The first stage was to examine the behaviour of the fabrics during shearing to establish both the shear stiffness and fabric locking angle. An automated strain analysis system, originally developed to characterise sheet metal formability, was then used to measure the fibre distribution within three-dimensional preforms. This allowed the relative importance of fabric deformation mechanisms to be established, and highlighted the limitations associated with the kinematic model.

Materials

A number of non-crimp (stitch-bonded) glass fabrics were used in this study. These are summarised in Table 1, which includes tow linear density in Tex (g/km), tow pitch (distance between centre lines) and fabric superficial density for each material. Examples of fabrics from the two manufacturers are shown in Fig. 1. The TT material (Fig. 1(a)) is held together using a tricot stitch, with the stitch oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the fibres. The BUC materials (Fig. 1(b)) contain a similar tricot stitch, with an additional chain stitch used to maintain each layer of unidirectional fibres within the fabric. Although the BUC materials were intended to be $\pm 45^\circ$, the samples actually had a ply angle of approximately $\pm 55^\circ$ due to fabric relaxation.

Table 1: Material data for Tech Textiles (TT) and Flemmings (BUC) non-crimp fabrics

Code	Tow linear density (Tex)	Tow pitch (mm)	Superficial density (g/m ²)
TT/936	600	1.3	936
BUC/403	408	2.0	403
BUC/440	408	1.8	440
BUC/545	408	1.5	545
BUC/600	408	1.3	600
BUC/682	408	1.2	682
BUC/784	900	2.3	784
BUC/800	600	1.5	800
BUC/1200	900	1.5	1200

Fig. 1: Non-crimp fabric constructions

FABRIC DRAPE MODELLING

Deformation Mechanisms

Reinforcement fabrics based on high modulus fibres can conform to non-developable surfaces via a number of mechanisms (as discussed in detail by Potter [1]). The most important mechanisms can be summarised as follows:

1. Inter-fibre shear—fibres rotate about their crossover points (stitch or weave centres) up to the limit of shear deformation (known as the “locking angle”).
2. Inter-fibre slip—fibres move relative to each other at the crossovers, so that the fabric is effectively stretched locally.
3. Fibre buckling—when the fabric is subjected to local in-plane compression, resulting in folds or wrinkles in the preform (likely to occur at the limit of shear/slip deformation).

The relative importance of each of the above mechanisms is likely to be fabric specific, and may be characterised experimentally using a number of techniques as described later in this paper.

Kinematic Drape Model

The majority of models of fabric deformation are based on a relatively simple approach, assuming that deformation is restricted to inter-fibre shear. This allows a kinematic mapping to be used to determine the deformed fibre architecture, and has been applied by a number of researchers to simulate the deformation of both fabric reinforcements and prepregs [eg. 2-4]. Fabric wrinkling may be anticipated by comparing the predicted local deformation to the measured fabric locking angle, thus allowing such problems to be accounted for at the design stage. Although in practice other deformation mechanisms may also occur, this simplified approach provides a useful design limit in which the effects of deformation on fibre orientations and volume fraction are maximised. Starting with two intersecting fibre paths, which determine the initial orientation of the material, each fibre crossover or “node” is located by solving the equations of intersection between the fabric and the surface. These equations can be solved explicitly if the surface is represented using flat patches (using the method described by Long & Rudd [4]).

FABRIC SHEAR TESTING

Whilst the modelling approach described above can be used to provide a rapid indication of the fibre architecture within the preform, it has no way of distinguishing different fabrics other than in the specification of the deformation limit (locking angle). The behaviour of fabrics subjected to shearing can be measured experimentally to determine the effective shear compliance. As well as providing a measure of the fabric locking angle, such tests can also be used to provide data for a mechanistic deformation model (eg. [5]). Fabric shear testing can be carried out in a parallelogram fixture (as shown in Fig. 2), in which the fabric sample is clamped on either two or four sides. The shearing force is applied in the bias direction while measuring the axial displacement using an instrumented loading frame.

Fig. 2: Parallelogram fixture for fabric shear testing

Typical results for a stitch-bonded (non-crimp) fabric reinforcement are shown in Fig. 3. Results are presented for specimens loaded both parallel and perpendicular to the stitching thread (as indicated in the inset figure). It is clear that this particular material exhibits significantly greater resistance to shear when loaded parallel to the stitch, which is under increasing tension throughout the test. The rapid increase in shear force as the shear angle approaches 60° is thought to indicate the onset of fibre locking, as wrinkles were clearly visible on fabric specimens towards the end of the tests. These results were produced at a crosshead speed of 100mm/min, although similar results were obtained at other rates in the range 68 to 1020 mm/min.

To establish the effect of fabric construction on shear properties, tests were carried out using a number of non-crimp fabrics with a range of tow spacings and linear densities (the BUC materials listed in Table 1). As has already been mentioned, these materials were actually $\pm 55^\circ$, so shear tests were carried out with samples clamped on two parallel sides with one set of fibres aligned in the direction of shear. For all materials, it was found that fibre locking occurred at a very low shear angle (approximately 15°) when loaded parallel to the tricot stitch, with shear forces typically double those measured with a perpendicular stitch. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between shear force and shear angle for specimens loaded perpendicular to the stitch. It is clear that an increase in tow linear density with constant pitch

(Fig. 4(a)) results in an increase in shear force. Similarly for constant linear density tows a decrease in pitch results in increased resistance to shear (Fig. 4(b)).

Fig. 3: Shear force versus shear angle for TT/936 non-crimp fabric

Skelton [6] defined the fabric shear stiffness as the ratio between shearing couple per unit area and shear angle. However as the graph of shear force versus angle is non-linear, a direct application of this relationship leads to a variation in shear stiffness throughout the test. It is more appropriate to calculate the shear stiffness over the linear portion of the graph using:

$$S = \frac{l d F_s}{l d \theta_s} \quad (1)$$

where l is the length of fabric in the direction of shear (250mm for these tests). This relationship was applied to the data presented in Fig. 4 over the range 8 to 32° shear. According to Skelton [6], the resistance to shear of a fabric is governed by friction at the tow crossovers, and should be proportional to the number of tow crossovers per unit area. However, whilst this may be applicable to materials with the same tow properties, when the linear density is varied it is more realistic to consider the effective area of each of the tow crossovers. Thus it may be expected that resistance to shear should be proportional to the area of tow crossovers per unit area of fabric. This is confirmed by Fig. 5, which shows that fabric shear stiffness varies almost linearly with the relative crossover area (calculated on the basis of a tow aspect ratio of 3:1). However whilst this is interesting it should not be considered critical to preform design, as the forces required to deform the fabrics were small in all cases.

(a) Varying tow linear density (16.9mm pitch)

(b) Varying tow pitch (408 Tex)

Fig. 4: Effect of fabric construction on shear force versus shear angle relationship

Fig. 5: Variation in shear stiffness with proportion of fibre crossovers for Flemmings fabrics (loaded perpendicular to stitch).

AUTOMATED STRAIN ANALYSIS

Although the above method can be used to examine the formability of fabrics during shearing, other deformation mechanisms are excluded by the nature of the test. To study the deformation of reinforcements during three-dimensional forming operations, a technique is required to measure the positions and orientations of fibres within a preform. Such a technique can be used to assess the relative importance of the available deformation mechanisms, and also provides a method for validating the drape model described earlier. To this end a method developed by Ford Motor Company to characterise sheet metal formability has been adapted to measure fabric deformation. This involves measuring the deformation of a square grid on the material surface, and is known as the CAMSYS Automated Strain Analysis and Measurement Environment (as shown schematically in Fig. 6). This can be used to determine the position of each grid intersection, from which local shear and slip data can be obtained (as described in our earlier paper [7]).

Fig. 6: Automated strain analysis and measurement environment schematic

To apply this technique to reinforcements, fabric samples were formed using a 100mm diameter punch mounted on a hydraulic press. Specimens were formed to a depth of 65mm at a punch velocity of 65mm/s, with constant clearance maintained at the clamped periphery to allow edge draw during forming. Deformed specimens were then rigidised using an aerosol varnish prior to analysis using the CAMSYS system. In each case, specimens were considered in four quadrants, two of which were effectively deformed parallel to the stitching thread and two perpendicular. Typical results for a non-crimp fabric are shown in Fig. 7, which compares the measured fibre pattern with the distribution predicted using the kinematic drape model. In both cases the surface is shaded to represent local shear, whilst for the measured pattern fibre segments are also shaded to indicate inter-fibre slip (calculated as percentage strain between intersections). On a qualitative level, it is clear that the predicted and measured fibre distributions agree reasonably well.

A quantitative comparison is made in Fig. 8, which shows the predicted and measured inter-fibre angles along the axis of maximum deformation (as indicated on the inset figure). There is generally a good agreement between the predicted and measured values, particularly for quadrants sheared parallel to the stitch. The predicted level of shear is slightly lower (ie. higher inter-fibre angle) for quadrants which were sheared parallel to the stitching thread, which may be due to the increased resistance to shear in this direction as demonstrated in Fig. 3. Minimum inter-fibre angles of 41° and 51° were measured respectively for deformation parallel and perpendicular to the stitch. These may be considered to be the effective locking angles for this material, as wrinkles were clearly visible around the base of the specimens. Inter-fibre slip of up to 10% was recorded in the same areas, suggesting that the pure shear assumption may be unsatisfactory in the most highly deformed regions.

The same technique was applied to the range of BUC fabrics (as described in Table 1). Typical inter-fibre angle data is compared with the kinematic model prediction in Fig.9. As noted in the previous section, these materials lock at a very low level of shear when deformed parallel to the stitching thread. In this case, the maximum shear angle measured in this direction was 12° . For the quadrants which were sheared perpendicular to the stitch, the measured level of shear was slightly greater than predicted by the drape simulation. This demonstrates that the significant deformation was restricted to 2 quadrants during the forming operation. Similar measurements made with various fabric constructions showed little or no effect on the deformed fibre distribution. This would suggest that the important parameter in simulating fabric drape is the fibre locking angle. Differences in fabric shear stiffness may be of relevance if forming loads are of concern, although in practice these are likely to be significantly lower than the forces generated during reinforcement compaction.

Fig. 7: Predicted (left) and measured (right) fibre patterns for hemisphere draped with TT/936

Fig. 8: Comparison of predicted and measured fibre angles for TT/936

Fig. 9: Comparison of predicted and measured fibre angles for BUC/800

CONCLUSIONS

This study has demonstrated two methods which can be used to characterise reinforcement formability. Fabric shear testing can be used to determine the effective shear stiffness, and may also indicate the fabric locking angle. However the latter is very much subject to interpretation, and in particular there is no obvious way to deduce the deformation limit from the shear force variation measured during the test. An automated strain analysis technique, adapted from sheet metal formability, can be used to measure the fibre distribution within a three-dimensional preform. This method allows a wider range of deformation mechanisms to be characterised, and also provides a quantitative method for validating a fabric drape simulation.

Each of these methods was applied to a range of non-crimp fabrics with various constructions. Stitch orientation, tow linear density and tow pitch were all found to have a significant affect on fabric shear stiffness, although only stitch orientation appeared to affect the fabric locking angle. The stitching thread also had a significant affect on the fibre distribution during three-dimensional forming, whereas other factors which influence fabric shear stiffness were not found to be significant. From these results it may be concluded that the most important parameter in characterising fabric formability is the locking angle, although it should be recognised that this may depend on the direction of shear deformation.

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